

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется процесс цифровой трансформации системы образования в Узбекистане. Будет освещена важность, возможности и проблемы внедрения цифровых технологий в образовательный процесс. Также представлены результаты исследований по развитию платформ электронного обучения, системы дистанционного обучения, цифровой грамотности и инновационных образовательных технологий. В статье анализируются проводимые реформы по повышению качества образования и стоящие перед ними проблемы, даются рекомендации по их решению.

Ключевые слова: цифровая трансформация, система образования, дистанционное обучение, платформы электронного обучения, инновационные технологии, цифровая грамотность;

Annotation. This article analyzes the process of digital transformation of the educational system in Uzbekistan. The importance, opportunities and problems of introducing digital technologies into the educational process are highlighted. The results of the study on the development of e-learning platforms, distance learning system, digital literacy and innovative educational technologies are also presented. The article analyzes the reforms carried out to improve the quality of education and the problems faced and gives recommendations for their solution.

Keywords: digital transformation, education system, distance education, e-

learning platforms, innovative technologies, digital literacy;

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada O‘zbekistonda ta’lim tizimining raqamli transformatsiyasi jarayoni tahlil qilinadi. Raqamli texnologiyalarni ta’lim jarayoniga joriy etishning ahamiyati, imkoniyatlari va muammolari yoritiladi. Shuningdek, elektron ta’lim platformalari, masofaviy ta’lim tizimi, raqamli savodxonlik va innovatsion ta’lim texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi bo‘yicha o‘tkazilgan tadqiqot natijalari keltirilgan. Maqolada ta’lim sifatini oshirish uchun amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar va duch kelinayotgan muammolar tahlil qilinib, ularni hal etish bo‘yicha tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Raqamli transformatsiya, ta’lim tizimi, masofaviy ta’lim, elektron ta’lim platformalari, innovatsion texnologiyalar, raqamli savodxonlik;

Introduction. In the modern world, the educational process is undergoing digital transformation at an accelerated pace. Uzbekistan is also not excluded from this global trend and is implementing large-scale reforms to digitize the education system. In this article, we will talk about the digital transformation of education in Uzbekistan, its advantages, problems and prospects.

Digital transformation is the process of optimizing and improving the effectiveness of educational processes using ICT.

Main part. The following measures are implemented in Uzbekistan regarding the digitalization of the educational sphere:

Through Ziyonet, UzEdu and other platforms, electronic textbooks, video tutorials and tests are being provided for students.

Online classes and distance learning systems are being developed.

Training on the basis of digital technologies.

The use of Smart boards, interactive whiteboards, tablets and computer technology is expanding.

The possibilities of using artificial intelligence and virtual reality technologies are being expanded.

Automation of the learning process.

Electronic diary and electronic journal systems are being introduced and the monitoring of the educational process is being relaxed.

Electronic libraries provide access to scientific and literary resources.

Digital transformation in the Uzbek education system provides the following advantages:

Personalized training-an opportunity is created to receive an education that matches the level and needs of each student's knowledge.

Distance learning opportunities-opportunities for quality education will expand for children living in remote areas.

Access to modern educational resources-through electronic libraries and educational platforms, students and teachers can use a wide range of knowledge resources.

Reduction of paper documents-saves time and funds due to electronic document management.

Problems faced and ways to solve them.

In the process of digital transformation, Uzbekistan faces the following difficulties:

Some schools do not have enough modern computer technology.

Internet speed and quality are not the same in all regions. Solution: infrastructure development in cooperation of the public and private sectors.

Results and discussions. Digital transformation of the educational system in Uzbekistan modern aims to improve the quality of Education, effectively use information resources and automate educational processes by introducing technologies into the educational process. The results of the studies carried out indicate the following:

1. The widespread introduction of e – learning platforms-students and teachers have been able to use Moodle, Google Classroom, Ziyonet and other electronic

systems in the learning process.

2. The development of distance education – in the context of a pandemic, the distance education system has developed rapidly and is still used today.

3. The development of interactive lesson methods – Virtual laboratories, the introduction of educational programs based on artificial intelligence-are increasing the effectiveness of the educational process.

4. The increase in the level of digital literacy – teachers and students are taking special courses to improve their skills in the use of modern technologies.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it is possible to say that the digital transformation of the educational system of Uzbekistan will expand the possibilities of obtaining modern knowledge and serve to make the future of young people brighter. As a result of the reforms carried out by the government, distance education opportunities increase and the educational process is reaching a qualitatively new level. In the future, the introduction of artificial intelligence, virtual reality and other advanced technologies into the educational process will further increase the effectiveness of Education.

The digital transformation of education is the guarantee of the competitive future of Uzbekistan. The successful implementation of this process will serve to increase the intellectual potential of our country and gain a worthy place in the world.

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